

Assessment of Examination Stress and Its Impact on Cognitive Function among Medical Students**Rishikesh Kumar¹, Sheela Kumari², Vijay Kumar Singh³, Bharat Kumar⁴, Chandra Mauleshwar Jha⁵, Devanand Kumar⁶**^{1,5,6}Junior Resident, Department of Physiology, Darbhanga Medical College, Laheriasarai, Darbhanga, 846001 (Bihar) India²Professor & HOD, Department of Physiology, Darbhanga Medical College, Laheriasarai, Darbhanga, 846001 (Bihar) India³Professor, Department of Physiology, Darbhanga Medical College, Laheriasarai, Darbhanga, 846001 (Bihar) India⁴Associate Professor, Department of Physiology, Darbhanga Medical College, Laheriasarai, Darbhanga, 846001 (Bihar) India

Received: 25-09-2024 / Revised: 23-10-2024 / Accepted: 26-11-2024

Corresponding Author: Dr. Sheela Kumari

Conflict of interest: Nil

Abstract:**Background:** Exam stress is a prevalent concern among medical students, potentially influencing their cognitive function and academic performance. This research evaluates student well-being in medical education by examining the correlation between stress levels and cognitive performance.**Method:** A total of 80 (40 males and 40 females) healthy MBBS students participated. A stress questionnaire was given and assessed. Cardiovascular parameters were also assessed. The ART and VRT were Recorded before (pre-examination setting) and after 3 months of examination (post-examination setting). The data were analysed by using SPSS 25.0 version.**Result:** Regardless of gender, all indicators, including PR, SBP, DBP, ART, VRT, and stress ratings, increased in the pre-examination setting. Female learners had elevated PR, while males showed increased stress scores and SBP in the pre-examination scenario. The prevalence of ART and VRT was higher in females than in males in both settings.**Conclusion:** The study concludes that the stress of exams negatively impacts the cognitive function of medical students. Female students are more affected than males. Therefore, it is recommended that early counseling is provided to students to reduce their stress levels.**Keywords:** Cardiovascular parameters, Cognitive function, Stress, Visual reaction time, and auditory reaction time.This is an Open Access article that uses a funding model which does not charge readers or their institutions for access and distributed under the terms of the Creative Commons Attribution License (<http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0>) and the Budapest Open Access Initiative (<http://www.budapestopenaccessinitiative.org/read>), which permit unrestricted use, distribution, and reproduction in any medium, provided original work is properly credited.**Introduction**

Examination stress is pervasive within academic settings, particularly among medical students subjected to an intense and demanding curriculum. The pressure to perform well in exams, the heavy workload, and high expectations often result in elevated stress levels. This stress is not merely a psychological burden; it can profoundly affect cognitive functions essential for learning, memory retention, and problem-solving. [1,2]

Cognitive functions, including attention, memory, and executive functions, are crucial for academic success, especially in a field as rigorous as medicine. However, these cognitive processes are susceptible to stress. When stress levels rise, the body's physiological responses can lead to disruptions in brain function, impairing the ability

to concentrate, recall information, and make sound decisions. This can create a vicious cycle where stress leads to poorer cognitive performance, increasing stress and further compromising academic outcomes. [3,4] Medical students are particularly vulnerable to this cycle due to the unique challenges of their training.

The need to assimilate vast amounts of information in a relatively short period, coupled with frequent high-stakes examinations, places significant demands on their cognitive resources. Moreover, the competitive nature of medical education can exacerbate feelings of stress and anxiety, making it more difficult for students to perform to their full potential. [5,6] Understanding the impact of exam stress on cognitive function is therefore critical. It

can provide insights into how stress management strategies can be tailored to medical students' specific needs, helping them optimize their cognitive abilities and improve their academic performance. This study seeks to explore the relationship between exam-related stress and cognitive function among medical students to identify potential interventions that could mitigate the adverse effects of stress and enhance overall well-being and academic success. [7,8]

This research aims to contribute to the growing literature on student well-being in medical education by examining the correlation between stress levels and cognitive performance. The findings may have broader implications for educational practices and mental health support services, highlighting the need for comprehensive approaches to managing stress in high-pressure academic environments.

Material and Methods

This study employed a cross-sectional design to investigate the relationship between exam-related stress and cognitive function among medical students. The research was conducted at the Department of Physiology of DMCH, Laheriasarai, and Darbhanga, India (May 2024 and August 2024). Ethical approval from the Institution Ethical Committee and written informed consent from the volunteers were obtained. 80 (40 males, 40 females) MBBS healthy students of the age group 18-24 years were selected based on inclusion and exclusion criteria who were appearing for the Internal Assessment Examination.

Inclusion criteria included healthy male and female medical students, and exclusion criteria included any history of neurological or psychiatric disorders, taking of medicines affecting emotional status and endocrinological disorder, any visual and auditory disorder, and addiction to tobacco or alcohol.

Procedure

Table 1: Comparison of stress score, cognitive, and cardiovascular parameters in the pre-and post-examination settings

Parameters	Pre-examination (n=80)	Post-examination (n=80)	p-value
PR (beats/min)	86.11±10.03	78.11±11.16	0.002
SBP (mmHg)	126.9±9.11	117.10±8.11	0.002
DBP (mmHg)	85.79±8.16	74.11±4.12	0.002
ART (ms)	183.13±17.21	164.21±26.19	0.003
VRT (ms)	215.11±21.11	192.54±30.93	0.002
Stress score	27.38±9.15	20.01±5.44	0.002

Data is mean±SD. Considered significant is p<0.05

Table 2 reveals a statistically significant increase in PR ($p<0.02$) among females compared to males. However, it was shown that stress ratings and systolic blood pressure ($p<0.05$) were substantially higher in males than in females during the pre-

This is a cross-sectional study where all students were instructed to be at the research laboratory at 8.45 am before their internal assessment examination. They were explicitly instructed to abstain from caffeinated beverages such as coffee or tea and rest for 15 minutes. During the experimental sessions, tests were conducted on 40 students on the 1st and 2nd days and 40 on the 3rd and 4th days.

The exams were completed 10 minutes before the examination. The students were administered a Stress Questionnaire consisting of 20 items, which was then collected after 10 minutes to evaluate their stress score. The scores were categorized as follows: 0-20 indicated reasonable control over stress, 21-40 indicated a low degree of stress, 41-60 indicated a medium level of stress, and 60-80 indicated a high level of stress. Anthropometric data, such as weight in kilos and height in millimeters, were evaluated using a standardized weighing machine and height measurement scale. The participants were evaluated for cardiovascular indicators, cognitive metrics, and stress levels at two periods. Two readings were taken: one before the final internal examination (pre-examination setting) and another after 3 months when no examination (post-examination setting).

Statistical Analysis

The data were examined using the statistical program SPSS version 25.0. Analyzed utilizing a paired t-test, the pre and post-data were examined. Pearson's correlation coefficient was utilized to do correlation analysis. The results of continuous measurements are provided as the mean±SD.

Results

Table 1 reveals that all indicators, including PR, SBP, DBP, VRT, stress ratings ($p<0.01$), and ART ($p<0.05$), exhibited a significant increase in the pre-examination environment compared to the post-examination setting, regardless of gender.

examination period. Table 2 also showed that ART and VRT were higher among females than males, regardless of the setting. However, the ART and VRT ($p<0.05$) showed a substantial rise in females compared to males in both circumstances.

Table 2: The impact of gender in a pre-examination scenario on stress score, cognitive and cardiovascular parameters

Parameters	Pre-examination (Male=40)	Pre-examination (Female=40)	p-value
PR (beats/min)	82.16±8.18	90.12±10.18	0.002
SBP (mmHg)	128.21±9.11	125.18±12.42	0.033
DBP (mmHg)	83.14±6.76	86.16±5.60	0.051
ART (ms)	176.40±21.32	187.35±19.11	0.032
VRT (ms)	206.52±18.78	219.48±21.39	0.038
Stress score	30.15±7.22	24.19±6.13	0.032

Data is mean±SD. Considered significant is p<0.05

Table 3 demonstrates a statistically significant increase in the delta PR (derived by subtracting the pre- and post-examination setting value) in females compared to males, regardless of the setting (p<0.05).

Table 3: Influence of gender on changes in cardiovascular parameters, cognitive parameters and stress scores

Parameters	Male=40	Female=40	p-value
Delta PR (beats/min)	-1.723±11.41	-11.113±11.119	0.002
Delta SBP (mmHg)	-9.112±11.331	-3.712±11.112	0.067
Delta DBP (mmHg)	-0.052±13.101	-1.841±7.152	0.411
Delta ART (ms)	-10.114±18.308	-13.515±32.131	0.547
Delta VRT (ms)	-21.141±14.181	-17.681±23.316	0.517
Delta Stress score	-7.217±6.017	-4.322±5.123	0.072

Data is mean±SD. Considered significant is p<0.05

Discussion

The current study revealed a substantial rise in PR (pulse rate), SBP (systolic blood pressure), DBP (diastolic blood pressure), ART (arterial response time), VRT (vascular response time), and stress ratings during the pre-examination period compared to the post-examination period. Elevated PR and BP, encompassing both systolic and diastolic blood pressure, result from heightened sympathetic activation. [9,10] The augmented release of adrenaline and glucocorticoid can increase ART (Adrenaline Response Time) and VRT (Vasopressin Response Time). These findings contrast the reports of other writers who observed a drop in ART before the examination. [8]

Our findings have a small connection to the integrated model, primarily grounded in the distraction model. [11] Research has also indicated that when faced with stressful situations, the cognitive system becomes overwhelmed, decreasing a person's attentional resources. [12] The impact of stress on decision-making and attention can be attributed to the activation of the sympathetic nervous system and the brain-pituitary-adrenocortical axis. The sympathetic nervous system and the brain-pituitary-adrenocortical axis can act directly or indirectly. The present study also found a substantial rise in stress scores before the examination compared to after the examination. These findings corroborate the assertions of earlier researchers that medical students experience daily stress due to academic pressures. [6,13,14] The present study demonstrates

that females exhibit higher PR, ART, and VRT levels in the pre-examination setting than males. However, the disparities in PR are particularly noteworthy. This finding aligns with other reports, as indicated by previous studies. [15] An elevation in adrenocorticotrophic hormone (ACTH) and vasopressin release can be attributed to the heightened secretion of epinephrine. [6,16] According to a prior study, stress levels were elevated among females as determined by stress questionnaires. [17]

Conversely, a separate study found no significant difference in stress levels between males and females. [18] The current study demonstrates a substantial rise in stress levels among males compared to females in pre-examination conditions. Additional validation of the stress questionnaire is necessary based on this outcome. In addition, the current study found no correlation between the students' internal evaluation scores and their pre-examination stress levels. Undertaking a future study to assess students' stress levels before exams would provide a complete understanding of the topic.

There is no notable disparity in PR (pulse rate), SBP (systolic blood pressure), DBP (diastolic blood pressure), and stress scores between males and females in post-examination environments. In both circumstances, the ART and VRT values are higher in females than males. Nevertheless, the VRT (Vasopressin Response Time) exhibited a noteworthy increase in females, potentially attributed to the hormonal fluctuations during the

menstrual cycle. Ovarian hormones extensively impact several brain regions, including cognitive function. [19,20] Females exhibited a notably more significant delta PR compared to males. However, no significant differences were observed in other metrics such as delta SBP, delta DBP, delta ART, delta VRT, and delta stress scores. The rise in PR (pulse rate) among females may be attributed to the activation of the hypothalamic-pituitary axis and autonomic nervous system in response to the stress induced by examinations. Consistent with previous research, this study finds that women experience more distress with the task compared to males.²¹

Conclusion

Our study has conducted initial research on the impact of stress on cognitive function and found that high levels of stress can impair cognitive functioning and perhaps hinder performance in exams. Additionally, it was noted that female students were more susceptible to stress, which negatively impacted their cardiovascular indicators, such as PR and cognitive parameters before exams. Identifying pupils prone to high stress will enable educators to address their needs adequately as soon as possible.

Acknowledgement

We are very thankful to all who have helped us to carry out this study. The authors thank MBBS students who participated voluntarily in the present study. The authors thank Aziz Writing Solutions (AWS) for assisting in manuscript preparation and publication.

References

- Rajendran V, Jayalalitha S, Adalarasu K. EEG based evaluation of examination stress and test anxiety among college students. *Irbm*. 2022; 43(5):349-61.
- Špiljak B, Vilibić M, Glavina A, Crnković M, Šešerko A, Lugović-Mihić L. A review of psychological stress among students and its assessment using salivary biomarkers. *Behavioral sciences*. 2022; 12(10):400.
- Alotaibi AD, Alosaimi FM, Alajlan AA, Abdulrahman KAB. The relationship between sleep quality, stress, and academic performance among medical students. *Journal of Family and Community Medicine*. 2020; 27(1):23-8.
- Gazzaz ZJ, Baig M, Al Alhendi BSM, Al Suliman MMO, Al Alhendi AS, Al-Grad MSH, et al. Perceived stress, reasons for and sources of stress among medical students at Rabigh Medical College, King Abdulaziz University, Jeddah, Saudi Arabia. *BMC medical education*. 2018; 18:1-9.
- Wadi MM, Yusoff MSB, Rahim AFA, Lah NAZN. Assessment Modalities That Provoke Test Anxiety among Medical Students. *Education in Medicine Journal*. 2022; 14(2).
- Bergmann C, Muth T, Loerbroks A. Medical students' perceptions of stress due to academic studies and its interrelationships with other domains of life: a qualitative study. *Medical education online*. 2019; 24(1):1603526.
- Preston R, Gratani M, Owens K, Roche P, Zimanyi M, Malau-Aduli B. Exploring the impact of assessment on medical students' learning. *Assessment & Evaluation in Higher Education*. 2020; 45(1):109-24.
- Moreira de Sousa J, Moreira CA, Telles Correia D. Anxiety, depression and academic performance: a study amongst Portuguese medical students versus non-medical students. *Acta medica portuguesa*. 2018; 31(9):454-62.
- Gavelin HM, Neely AS, Dunås T, Eskilsson T, Järholm LS, Boraxbekk C-J. Mental fatigue in stress-related exhaustion disorder: Structural brain correlates, clinical characteristics and relations with cognitive functioning. *NeuroImage: Clinical*. 2020; 27:102337.
- Moir F, Yelder J, Sanson J, Chen Y. Depression in medical students: current insights. *Advances in medical education and practice*. 2018:323-33.
- Vivas E, Nascimento M, Rocha S. The performance anxiety influence on the motor coordination levels: A literature mini-review. *Int J Educ Res*. 2021; 3:1-5.
- Stevens JS, Jovanovic T. Role of social cognition in post-traumatic stress disorder: A review and meta-analysis. *Genes, Brain and Behavior*. 2019; 18(1):e12518.
- Mishra P, Panigrahi M, Ankit D. Cognition and alertness in medical students: effects of a single night of partial sleep deprivation. *Annals of neurosciences*. 2020; 27(2):57-62.
- Tian-Ci Quek T, Wai-San Tam W, X. Tran B, Zhang M, Zhang Z, Su-Hui Ho C, et al. The global prevalence of anxiety among medical students: a meta-analysis. *International journal of environmental research and public health*. 2019; 16(15):2735.
- Hammoud S, Karam R, Mourad R, Saad I, Kurdi M. Stress and heart rate variability during university final examination among Lebanese students. *Behavioral sciences*. 2018; 9(1):3.
- Kalantari S, Tripathi V, Kan J, Rounds JD, Mostafavi A, Snell R, et al. Evaluating the impacts of color, graphics, and architectural features on wayfinding in healthcare settings using EEG data and virtual response testing. *Journal of Environmental Psychology*. 2022; 79:101744.
- Wang J, Li D, Ye Y, Qiu Y, Liu J, Huang L, et al. A fluorescent metal-organic framework for

- food real-time visual monitoring. *Advanced Materials*. 2021; 33(15):2008020.
18. Bhavani Nivetha M, Ahmed M, Prashantha B. Perceived stress and source of stress among undergraduate medical students of Government Medical College, Mysore. *International Journal of Community Medicine and Public Health*. 2018; 5(8):3513.
 19. Armbruster D, Grage T, Kirschbaum C, Strobel A. Processing emotions: Effects of menstrual cycle phase and premenstrual symptoms on the startle reflex, facial EMG and heart rate. *Behavioural brain research*. 2018; 351:178-87.
 20. Schmalenberger KM, Eisenlohr-Moul TA, Würth L, Schneider E, Thayer JF, Ditzen B, et al. A systematic review and meta-analysis of within-person changes in cardiac vagal activity across the menstrual cycle: implications for female health and future studies. *Journal of clinical medicine*. 2019; 8(11):1946.
 21. Santl J, Shiban Y, Plab A, Wüst S, Kudielka BM, Mühlberger A. Gender differences in stress responses during a virtual reality trier social stress test. *International Journal of Virtual Reality*. 2019; 19(2):2-15.